

Faunistic of Butterflies (Lepidoptera: Papilionidae from District Battagram, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

This study was conducted to contribute to the butterfly fauna of District Battagram. Butterflies were collected from various localities of district battagram from March 2020 to March 2021. The study area was divided into different localities, namely Ajmera, Thakot, Kuzabanda, Paimal, Shamlai, tehsil Allai, Tailoos, Biari, Sakargah Rashang and Bateela. A total of 120 specimens were collected which were identified into 17 genera and 21 species from four families: Nymphalidae, Pieridae, Lycaenidae and Papilionidae, covering 48%, 24%, 24% and 4% respectively. Family Nymphalidae included 10 species: *Junonia orithya*, *Junonia hierta*, *Junonia almana*, *Limenitis trivena*, *Vanessa cardui*, *Vanessa indica*, *Phalanta phalantha*, *Danaus chrysippus*, *Lasiommata schakra* and *Aulocera saraswati*. The Pieridae family included 5 species: *Pontia daplidice*, *Pieris brassicae*, *Eurema hecabe*, *Colias fieldii* and *Colias erate*. The Lycaenidae family comprised of 5 species: *Tarucus theophrastus*, *Lampides boeticus*, *Lycaena phleas*, *Aricia agestis* and *Polyommatus pseuderos*. Meanwhile, family Papilionidae was represented by a single species *Papilio bianor*. During the current study, *Junonia hierta* was recorded as the highest occurring species. This research significantly contributes to the Butterfly fauna of Battagram.

Keywords: Butterflies, Diversity, Battagram, Animals

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INTRODUCTION

Butterflies, together with coleoptera, are among the most varied and well-known insect groups in the world. They are distributed all across the planet, save in Antarctica (Hasan, 1997). Butterflies may be effective ecosystem bioindicators because they are sensitive to changes in environmental factors such as temperature, microclimate, and the presence of plants for oviposition and development of larva (Haroon et al., 2014). Today, experts are closely monitoring butterflies for signals of climate change and habitat destruction (Hasan, 1994). Butterflies account for only 11 percent of all species of lepidopteran, according to Shields (1989). More than 19,000 butterfly species have been recorded globally

(Heppner, 1998). There have been 440 butterfly species documented in Pakistan to far (Tshikolovets and Pagès, 2016; Awan et al., 2020).

Various researchers have concentrated on different aspects of entomology, such as butterfly distribution (Afshan et al., 2015; Khan et al., 2014; Mengal et al., 2017; Shah and Rafi, 2016; Taj et al., 2022; Yu-Feng et al., 2020; Rehman et al., 2023). Battagram is an area in Pakistan's Hazara Division, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province. Battagram District, located in the western Himalayan region of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, has a total area of 1,301 km² (Haq, 2012). The district shares geographical boundaries with Kohistan to the north, Mansehra to the east and southeast, Torghar to the south, and the Shangla to the west (Muhammad, 2003). According to the Census Report, the population of Battagram District is 476,749 people, with an annual growth rate of 2.33%. The district is divided into two sub-divisions, or Tehsils: Allai and Battagram. Butterfly data on Instagram is quite unusual. Bibi et al. (2022a, b) investigated the butterfly fauna of Battagram and identified nine species. The present investigation aims to learn more about and contribute to the butterfly fauna of Battagram.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

The study was carried out in the Battagram district, and the study area was divided into 10 survey sites based on geography and environmental factors. Five sites were selected from each tehsil. Specifically, from Tehsil Battagram, the selected sites were Ajmera, Thakot, Kuzabanda, Paimal, and Shamlai. Similarly and from tehsil Alai; the chosen sites included Tailos, Biarai, Sakargaah, Rashang, and Bateela (Figure 1).

MATERIALS AND TOOLS

The study materials comprised aerial nets, chloroforms, plastic bottles, DSLR cameras, entomological pins, Thermo-col sheets, butter papers, microscopes, naphthalene balls, register books, plastic sheets, GPS, android applications, and measuring scales.

COLLECTIONS AND PRESERVATION

For conducting surveys and sampling, every site was visited every two weeks for one year, from March 2020 to March 2021. Different sites were observed daily from 6 am to 11 am and 2 pm to 5 pm. Butterfly specimens were collected randomly using a specially designed insect net. After capturing the butterflies in the aerial net, the captured specimens were either killed by pressing their thorax or kept in chloroform for killing. To facilitate further analysis of these collected specimens, they were stored in butter boxes and labeled with complete data, including the month, locality, time, date, latitude, longitude, and humidity. After collection, these specimens were dried in sunlight and then pinned with hairpins onto thermocol sheets, along with naphthalene powder or balls, and covered with plastic sheets.

Figure 1: Study Area Map: District Battagram.

IDENTIFICATIONS

For identification purpose, all specimens were examined using a stereomicroscope, and their characteristics were analyzed by consulting relevant literature, (Bibi et al., 2021; Mengal et al., 2017; Roberts, 2001; Sabir et al., 2000; Taj et al., 2022; Yu-Feng et al., 2020; Ahmad et al., 2022; Rehman et al., 2023) and also with help of identified specimens housed at National Insect Museum (NIM), National Agriculture Research Center Islamabad (NARC).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the current survey, 120 specimens of butterflies were collected from the two Tehsils of District Battagram, namely Alai and Battagram, over a one-year period from March 2020 to March 2021. Collected specimens were classified into 4 families, 17 genera and 21 species. The dominant family Nymphalidae which comprised of 3 subfamilies; Nymphalinae, Danainae and Satyrinae. This family included a total 10 species: *Junonia orithya*, *Junonia hierta*, *Junonia almana*, *Limnitis trivena*, *Vanessa cardui*, *Vanessa indica*, *Phalanta phalantha*, *Danaus chrysippus*, *Lasiommata schakra* and *Aulocera saraswati*. The family Pieridae consisted of 2 subfamilies namely Pierinae and Coliadinae and a total 5 species: *Pontia daplidice*, *Pieris brassicae*, *Eurema hecabe*, *Colias fieldii* and *Colias erate*. Family Lycaenidae comprised 5 species: *Tarucus theophrastus*, *Lampides boeticus*, *Lycaena phlease*, *Aricia agestis* and *Polyommatus pseuderos*. The family Papilionidae was represented by a single species *Papilio bianor*. During

the current study *Junonia almanac* was reported very common while *Tarucus theophrastus* was rarely observed. In their Bibi et al (2022a, b) study, focused on the butterfly fauna of Battagram and identified a total of 9 species, namely *Cynthia cardui*, *Danaus chrysippus*, *Junonia orithya*, *Papilio demoleus*, *Papilio polytes*, *Colias croceus*, *Pieris ajaka*, *Pontia daplidice* and *Pieris napi*. Out of these, *Junonia orithya*, *Danaus chrysippus*, and *Pontia daplidice* had previously been documented in District Battagram by Bibi et al. (2022a, b). In the current study, the remaining 18 species identified in the area were reported for the first time, bringing the total number of species in the region to 27. This research significantly contributes to the understanding of the butterfly fauna in Battagram (Table 1 and Figure 2).

Figure 2: Graph showing number of butterfly species in each family within study area of Battagram.

Table 2: Battagram Study Area Butterfly Species Checklist.

Family	Sub Family		Scientific name	Common name
Nymphalidae	Nymphalinae	1	<i>Junonia orithya</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Blue pansy
		2	<i>Junonia hierta</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	Yellow pansy
		3	<i>Junonia almana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Peacock pansy
		4	<i>Limenitis trivena</i> (Moore, 1864)	Indian white admiral
		5	<i>Vanessa cardui</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Painted lady
		6	<i>Vanessa indica</i> (Herbst, 1794)	Indian Red admiral
		7	<i>Phalanta phalantha</i> (Drury, 1773)	Common leopard
	Danainae	8	<i>Danaus chrysippus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Plain Tiger
	Satyrinae	9	<i>Aulocera saraswati</i> (Kollar, 1844)	Striated Satyr
		10	<i>Lasiommata schakra</i> (Kollar, 1844)	Common wall Brown
Pieridae	Pierinae	11	<i>Pontia daplidice</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Bath white
		12	<i>Pieris brassicae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Large White
	Coliadinae	13	<i>Eurema hecabe</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Common grass Yellow
		14	<i>Colias fieldii</i> (Menetries, 1855)	Dark clouded Yellow
		15	<i>Colias erate</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	Pale Clouded Yellow
Lycaenidae		16	<i>Tarucus theophrastus</i> (Evans, 1932)	Indian Pieort
		17	<i>Aricia agestis</i> (Moore, 1865)	Orange-bordered Argus

	Lycaeninae	18	<i>Lampides boeticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	pea Blue
		19	<i>Lycaena phleasa</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Common copper
		20	<i>Polyommatus pseuderos</i> (Moore, 1879)	Kashmir Meadow Blue
Papilionidae	Papilioninae	21	<i>Papilio bianor</i> (Cramer, 1777)	Common Peacock

Order Lepidoptera
Family Nymphalidae
Sub-family Nymphalinae

1. *Junonia orithya* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Blue Pansy

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Allai, 24.iv.2020, Biari, 4.v.2020, Bateela, 12.V.2020, Ajmera, 21.V.2020 Thakot, 7.iii.2021. Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks; This species already reported from various localities including Lahore (Ahsan and Iqbal, 1975), Murree (Roberts, 2001) Buner (Naz *et al.*, 2001), Lower Dir (Khan *et al.*, 2016), Quetta (Mengal *et al.*, 2017), Shangla (Ahmad *et al.*, 2022) and Battagram (Bibi *et al.*, 2022).

2. *Junonia hierta* (Fabricius, 1798)

Yellow Pansy

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Rashang, 17-viii.2020, Tailoos, 9-ix.2020, Kuzabanda, 1.x.2020, Paimal, 14-ix.2020, Shamlai, 5-ix.2020. Coll. Sanaullah

Remarks; Previously this species has been reported from many localities namely Lahore (Ahsan and Iqbal, 1975), Rawalpindi and Islamabad (Iqbal, 1978), Sindh (Mal *et al.*, 2014) and Shangla (Ahmad *et al.*, 2022).

3. *Junonia almana* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Peacock Pansy

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Allai, 12.iv.2020, 21.v.2020, 18.vii.2020, 19.viii.2020, 24.ix.2021, .vii.2021; Rashang 11.vi.2020, Tailoos, 9.iii.2021, Biari, 21.vii.2020, 21.v.2020, 18.vii.2020, 19.viii.2020, Bateela, 9.viii.2020, Paimal, 12.vii.2020, 10.vi.2020, Shamlai, 29.vii.2020, Kuzabanda, 13.vi.2020, 19.vii.2020, 14.viii.2020, 19, 20, 21.ix.2021. Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks; This species already reported from Lahore (Ahsan and Iqbal, 1975), Rawalpindi and Islamabad (Iqbal, 1978), Sindh (Mal *et al.*, 2014), Charsadda (Haroon *et al.*, 2014) and Shangla (Ahmad *et al.*, 2023)

4. *Limenitis trivena* (Moore, 1864)

Indian white admiral

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Sakargah, 4.ix.;2020, Biari, 7.vi.2020, Bateela, 11.vi.2020, Ajmera, 21.vi.2020, 7.iii.2021. Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks; It was previously reported from Nathi Gali (Tshikolovets and Pagès, 2016).

5. *Vanessa cardui* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Painted lady

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Allai, 19-viii.2020 Tailoos, 21.ix.2020, Kuzabanda, 10.ix.2020, Paimal, 12.vii.2020, Shamlai 5.x.2020.

Remarks; It was previously reported from Lahore (Ahsan and Iqbal, 1975), Rawalpindi and Islamabad (Iqbal, 1978), Buner (Naz *et al.*, 2001), Mansehra (Perveen and Fazal, 2013), Charsadda (Yu-Feng *et al.*, 2020). Shangla (Ahmad *et al.*, 2023), Battagram (Bibi *et al.*, 2022).

6. *Vanessa indica* (Herbst, 1794)

Indian Red Admiral

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Sakargah, 4.ix.;2020, Biari, 7.vi.2020, Bateela, 11.vi.2020, Ajmera, 21.vi.2020, 7-iii.2021. Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks: It was reported from Lahore (Ahsan and Iqbal, 1975). Recently this species was reported from Haripur (bibi *et al.*, 2022) and Shangla (Ahmad *et al.*, 2023)

7. *Phalanta phalantha* (Drury, 1773)

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Allai, 24.iv.2020, Biari, 4.v.2020, Bateela, 12.v.2020, Ajmera, 21.vi.2020, Thakot, 18.vi.2020, 7-iii.2021. Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks; It has been documented from Rawalpindi and Islamabad (Iqbal, 1978), Kotli, Mirpur Bhimber, Muzaffarabad (AJK) (Khan *et al.*, 2007), Kohat (Perveen and Ahmad, 2012), and Shangla (Ahmad *et al.*, 2023).

Subfamily Danainae

8. *Danaus chrysippus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Plain Tiger

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Sakargah, 13.ix.2020, 3.vii.2021, Rashang, 11.vi.2020, Tailoos, 29.iii.2021, Biari, 21.vii.2020, Bateela, 29.viii.2020, Paimal, 8.vi.2020, Shamlai, 29.vii.2020, Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks; It was reported from Lahore (Ahsan and Iqbal, 1975), Rawalpindi and Islamabad (Iqbal, 1978), Buner (Naz *et al.*, 2001), Malakand and Swat (Inyatullah *et al.*, 2002); Mansehra (Perveen and Fazal, 2013), Shangla (Ahmad *et al.*, 2023), and Battagram (Bibi *et al.*, 2022).

Subfamily Satyrinae

9. *Aulocera saraswati* (Kollar, 1844)

Striated satyr

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram, Allai, 4.iv.2020, Biari, 24.vii.2020, Bateela, 2.viii.2020, Ajmera, 21.iv.2020 Thakot, 18.vi.2020, 7-ii.2021. Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks: It was reported from Kaghan and Baragali (Tshikolovets and Pagès, 2016).

10. *Lasiommata schakra* (Kollar, 1844)

Common Wall Brown

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Sakargah, 13.x.2020, Biari, 14.vii.2020, Bateela, 10.vi.2020 Ajmera, 21.ix.2020, 17-vii.2021. Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks: Abbasi *et al.*, (2019) reported this species from Dhirkot, Azad Kashmir.

Family Pieridae

Subfamily Pierinae

11. *Pontia daplidice* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Bath white

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Sakargah, 27.vi.2020, Biari, 19.vi.2020, Bateela, 2.vii.2020. Coll. Waqas: Ajmera, 7.viii.2020, Thakot, 18.vi.2020, 7-iii.2021. Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks; It has been reported from Rawalpindi, Islamabad and Murree hills (Hasan, 1997), Azad Kashmir, Poonch (Khan *et al.*, 2007), Upper Dir, Doag Dara (Attaullah *et al.*, 2018), Battagram (Bibi *et al.*, 2022) and Swat (Rehman *et al.*, 2023)

12. *Pieris brassicae* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Large Cabbage white

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Sakargah, 9.ix.2020, Biari, 13.ix.2020, Bateela, 18.ix.2020, Ajmera, 21.vii.2020, Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks;

It has been recorded from Azad Kashmir (Khan *et al.*, 2004), from Rawalpindi (Malik, 1970) and Swat (Rehman *et al.*, 2023).

Subfamily Coliadinae

13. *Eurema hecabe* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Common grass Yellow

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Thakot, 18.vi.2020, 8-vii.2020. Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks: Previously this species has been reported from Kohat (Parveen, 2012), Buner (Naz *et al.*, 2001), Lahore (Ahsan and Iqbal, 1975), Rawalpindi and Islamabad (Iqbal, 1978), Malakand Agency (Inayatullah *et al.*, 2002) and Swat (Rehman *et al.*, 2023).

14. *Colias fieldii* (Menetries, 1855)

Dark Clouded Yellow

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Thakot, 26.vi.2020, Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks; This species has been previously reported from Chitral (Leslic and Evans, 1903), Lahore (Ahsan and Iqbal, 1975), Rawalpindi and Islamabad (Iqbal, 1978) and Buner (Naz *et al.*, 2001) and Swat (Rehman *et al.*, 2023).

15. *Colias erate* (Fabricius, 1793)

Pale Clouded Yellow

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Sakargah, 24.iv.2020, Biari, 3. viii.2020, Bateela, 2.xi.2020, Ajmera, 21.xii.2020 Thakot, 18.xii.2020, Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks; This species has been previously reported from Sindh (Malik, 1970), Malakand (Inayatullah *et al.*, 2002), Upper Dir (Attaullah *et al.*, 2018), Abbotabad (Taj *et al.*, 2022) and Swat (Rehman *et al.*, 2023).

Family Lycaenidae

Subfamily Lycaeninae

16. *Tarucus theophrastus* (Evans, 1932)

Indian Pieort

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Sakargah, 3.vii.2020, Biari, 24.x.2020, Bateela, 9.x.2020, Ajmera, 21.xi.2020 Thakot, 18.vi.2020, 8-iii.2021. Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks: This species has been previously reported from Thakot (Tshikolovets and Pagès, 2016)

17. *Aricia agestis* (Moore, 1865)

Orange-bordered Argus

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Sakargah, 4.vii.2020, Biari, 14.iv.2020, Thakot, 18.vi.2020, 7-iii.2021. Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks: This species has been reported from Quetta (Mengal *et al.*, 2017), Swat, Kohistan, Muree, Punjab (Roberts, 2001).

18. *Lampides boeticus* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Pea Blue

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Sakargah, 24.ix.2021, Rashang, 11.vi.2020, Tailoos, 9.iii.2021, Biari, 21.vii.2020, Bateela, 9.viii.2020, Paimal, 8.vi.2020 Shamlai, 29.vii.2020, Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks; Previously this species has been recorded from Rawalpindi (Roberts, 2001).

19. *Lycaena phleas* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Common copper

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Sakargah, 24.iv.2020, Biari, 4.v.2020, Bateela, 12.v.2020, Ajmera, 21.v.2020, Thakot, 18.vi.2020, 7-iii.2021. Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks; This species has been previously reported from Buner (Naz *et al.*, 2001), Malakand Agency and Swat (Inayatullah *et al.*, 2002).

20. *Polyommatus pseuderos* (Moore, 1879)

Kashmir Meadow Blue

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram: Allai, 24.ix.2021, 13.vii.2021; Rashang 11.vi.2020, Tailoos, 9.iii.2021, Biari, 21.vii.2020, Bateela, 9. viii.2020, Paimal, 8.vi.2020 Shamlai 29.vii.2020. Coll. Rahman.

Remarks: Previously this species has been recorded from Shogran (Tshikolovets and Pagès, 2016).

Family Papilionidae

Subfamily Papilioninae

20. *Papilio bianor* (Cramer, 1777)

Common Peacock

Material Examined: Pakistan: Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Battagram; Thakot, 18.vi.2020, 7.vii.2020. Coll. Sanaullah.

Remarks; This species has been previously reported from Murree (Hasan, 1994), Swat (Inayatullah *et al.*, 2002) and Chitral (Leslic and Evans, 1903), Lower Dir (Khan, 2016).

CONCLUSION

In the present study, twenty-one species of butterflies from four families were documented. The findings revealed that Battagram is a highly rich biodiversity hotspot.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

All authors have declared that they have no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this article.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION

SA Mehmood and Sanaullah Designed the study, Sanaullah made Collection, QU, ABR Organized data, WA wrote and formatted Manuscript, MAR and SA Mehmood supervised the study

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